

Development of Thermoplastic Cutting Tool Using Resistive Heater and Digital PI controller

(Pembangunan Alat Pemotongan Thermoplastik Untuk Splint Menggunakan Alat Pemanasan Rintangan dan Pengawal PI Digital)

Yoon Heng, Yap^a, Kok Beng, Gan^{a*} & Siaw Chui,Chai^b

^aDepartment of Electrical, Electronic & Systems Engineering, Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

^bOccupational Therapy Program, Faculty of Health Sciences, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the hardware development of thermoplastic cutting tool. A splint or thermoplastic is a material which is used to support, restrict motion of a part of the body. Currently, occupational therapists use all-purpose snips to cut splint material into suitable size under room temperature. This causes hand pain to the therapist because the splint materials have different thickness and it is a hard material under room temperature. Therefore, the aims of this paper are to develop a cutting tool that is portable and capable of softening/cutting the splint materials. A temperature control system was designed and the performance of this tool is evaluated. An experiment is carried out to compare the effectiveness of heat generation between thermoelectric effect and resistive heating by using a commercial analog PI controller. The data obtained is resampled to offset the temperature. A digital PI controller is developed after the selection of heating element. The Ziegler Nichols second method is applied in the controller design. It was found that the heating tool works well at the target temperature. A PCB circuit board is made for this prototype. The prototype is packaged nicely onto a pair of scissors by using 3D printing. The splint materials can be softened in less than 10 seconds and can be cut.

Keywords: Thermoplastic; Thermoelectric Effect; Resistive Heating; Temperature Control System; PI controller;

ABSTRAK

Kajian ini berfokus kepada pembangunan alat pemotongan termoplastik. Splint atau termoplastik merupakan sesuatu bahan yang dapat memberikan sokongan kepada pesakit untuk melindungi anggota badan yang lemah dan patah. Ahli terapi menggunakan sepasang gunting untuk memotong bahan splint kepada saiz yang sesuai menyebabkan mereka mengalami kesakitan tangan kerana bahan ini mempunyai ketebalan yang berbeza dan ia merupakan bahan yang keras jika tidak dilembutkan pada suhu yang tinggi. Oleh itu, objektif kajian ini adalah untuk mereka bentuk alat pemotong yang mudah alih serta mampu melembutkan dan memotong bahan splint. Selain itu, satu sistem kawalan rintangan dikaji dalam kajian ini. Pengawal PI direka setelah cara penghasilan haba yang sesuai ditentukan. Kaedah Ziegler Nichols diguna pakai dalam rekabentuk pengawal PI. Pengawal PI yang dihasilkan dapat berfungsi pada suhu yang ditetapkan. PCB direka dan kaedah cetakan 3D diguna pakai bagi menyempurnakan prototaip ini. Bahan splint juga dapat dilembutkan dalam masa 10 saat sebelum digunting.

Kata kunci: Termoplastik; Kesan Termoelektrik; Pemanasan Rintangan; Sistem Kawalan Suhu; Pengawal PI

INTRODUCTION

A splint is used to support broken part of a person's body by changing its shape and size since 1750. The application of a splint is found to be useful until today. There are several materials that can be used to produce splint material such as fiberglass, celastic, plastic foam and thermoset material. Due to some limitations, thermoplastic is introduced in 1960 to produce splint materials (Fess 2002). Thermoplastic is a material which

will change its physical characteristics according to temperature. It is a soft material at high temperature and a hard material when the temperature goes low (DBP 2005). Currently hot water bath, steam, dry heating, heating gun and heating pan are the methods that used to soften thermoplastic. The splints come with different thickness which is 2.4mm, 3.2mm and 4.8mm (Multicast 2018). Before splinting process,

occupational therapist cut splints into small pieces by using all purpose snip. This causes hand pain to the therapist due to the hardness and thickness of splint materials under room temperature. During splinting process, occupational therapists draw a pattern on thermoplastics according to patients' part before immersed them in hot water for several minutes. A pair of scissors is used to cut the soften materials into desired shapes. This process is repeated for several times (Solutions 2015).

To create a heating tool to soften the splint material, two important criteria's are needed to be considered which are heating element and controller. There are two ways to generate heat which are using thermoelectric effect and resistive heating.

Thermoelectric effect is a phenomena in which conversion of temperature differences to electric voltage or vice versa occurs (Zhang & Zhao 2015). Peltier module is the most common module that generates heat using thermoelectric effect. In recent studies, Peltier module is used together with controller, temperature sensor and microcontroller to control and maintain temperature of the module at 80 degree Celsius. The effectiveness of Peltier module is evaluated. It is found that Peltier module works very well below temperature of 80 degree Celsius. Therefore, it is applicable to the products such as iron and hair dryer. This paper proves that Peltier module can reach to a maximum of 80 degree Celsius within 180 seconds (Kumar et al. 2015).

Peltier module is used together with heat sink, cooling fan and heat pipe to develop a storage tank water heater. The operating temperature of Peltier module is maintained at 85 degree Celsius. This paper shows that Peltier modules can be an effective way to develop storage tank water heater (Harata et al. 2001). However, it required a good cooling system to quickly settle down the temperature of the module continuously to prevent the module from overheating.

Resistive heating is a process to generate heat by allowing current to flow through a resistive element (Lupi et al. 2015). Cartridge heater is the most common heating element to perform resistive heating. It consists of metal heating resistor wound around a ceramic core. Therefore it is able to generate heat up to 750 degree Celsius. Normally a hole is drilled on a metal. Cartridge heater is placed into the hole to provide the maximum transfer of heat to the metal (Oppelt et al. 2012). This allows the metal to receive the maximum amount of heat during heating process and reach the target temperature in a very short time.

Resistive heating is applied in the study of steam generator for domestic steam cleaner. The application of cartridge heater in steam cleaner is cheaper, lighter and effective compare to spray boiling steam generator. This paper success to

produce a steam generator which can generate heat in a very short time. It improves the performance of domestic steam cleaner (Shen et al. 2010). Resistive heater is better than Peltier module in terms of generate heat at a very high temperature.

A research in formation of superplastic using resistive heating is done in year 2011. The aims of this paper are to improve the efficiency and reduce the consuming energy. It uses less than a minute to reach the target temperature which is 400 degree Celsius to form superplastic (Li et al. 2011). Resistive heating can easily reach a higher temperature in a shorter time compare to Peltier module.

There are several types of control system. The most common are PI and PID controller. Khan et al. (2018) use PI controller to control temperature of a heating pad. Digital PI controller is used in this paper. Transfer function of the overall system is determined. The value of proportional constant, K_p and integral constant, K_i is determined using Root Locus technique. This system is able to maintain the heating pad at 50 degree Celsius and the steady state error is very low. Therefore, it is suitable to implement PI controller to control temperature.

Hondianto et al. (2016) use PID controller in water heating system. The aims of this paper are to modify the current technique in order to improve the performance of PID controller. The new technique used is Model Driven PID. The results are taken to compare with the conventional PI and PID controller. This research concluded that the new technique is able to reduce overshoot and time taken to achieve stability of the system.

Álvarez de Miguel et al. (2017) uses PI and PID controller to design a electric air heater. Performance of PI and PID controller is compared in this research by setting different K_p , K_i and K_d values. This paper concludes that PI and PID controller are applicable during low and high air flow rate. PI controller is more effective due to its low steady state error.

The aims of this paper are to develop a cutting tool that is portable and capable of softening/cutting splint materials. A temperature control system is designed and the performance of this tool is evaluated. Resistive heater and PI controlling technique are used in this paper due to their effectiveness and suitability.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 and Figure 2 are the block diagram and schematic of the developed system. A digital PI controller is designed in this research. The current flow to the heater is controlled by using Pulse Width Modulation (PWM). BJT and MOSFET are used to limit the current flow to the heater. The temperature sensor is used to read temperature and

provide feedback to the PI controller. Buttons are used to select different temperature. The output is shown by using OLED screen. In order to choose a suitable heater for this research, an experiment is conducted between Peltier module and cartridge heater to compare the performance of both heaters. The evaluation has been carried out by using a commercial analog PI controller. Ahmed et al. (2017) uses two different tuning method which is Ziegler Nichols second method and manual tuning method to automate a solar water heating system. From his paper, it is found that Ziegler Nichols second method is better. The values of proportional gain and integral gain obtained are more accurate in order to improve system's stability.

FIGURE 1. Block diagram of the system

FIGURE 2. Schematic of the system

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the placement of the heater with a metal bar. The proportional gain, K_p is set to 5.5, 13, 25 and 40. The temperature is set to 70 degree Celsius. The results obtained are saved in Microsoft Excel and graphs are plotted by using MATLAB. A thermocouple meter is used to measure the real temperature of the metal bar. The data is resampled to offset the temperature value. The performance of Peltier module and cartridge heater is compared and evaluated. The heated metal bar is placed onto splint materials to observe the changes.

FIGURE 3. Placement of cartridge heater into metal bar

FIGURE 4. Placement of metal bar on Peltier module

FIGURE 5. Flow chart of digital PI controller

Figure 5 shows the program flow chart of the digital PI controller. Cartridge heater is used in this developed system. The PI controller received input from the user and set a set point as a reference temperature. It starts to read temperatures from the temperature sensor and calculate error difference in order to control the current flow to the cartridge heater through transistors. The controller is tested with different temperatures, which are 70, 80, 90 and 100 degree Celsius. The performance of the controller is evaluated based on the its system response. A PCB is designed for this research by using Orcad Cadance and the prototype is packaged nicely onto a pair of scissors by using 3D printing.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 and Table 2 show the system response of resistive heater and thermoelectric heater at different gain. Their response is the most stable at $K_p=40$. Figure 6 shows the graph of comparison between two heating method at $K_p=40$. Thermoelectric effect has a better response than resistive heating in terms of rise time, peak time, percentage overshoot and steady state error.

However, Peltier module reached its maximum heat transfer easily. In this situation, the hot layer will transfer heat to the cold side. This is not recommended and a large cooling fan or water cooling system is needed to cool down the module. Thus, it increased the overall size of the prototype. Therefore, cartridge heater is selected in this paper. Figure 7 shows the temperature offset measurement for the metal bar. A thermocouple meter is used to read the real temperature of the metal bar. The reading is compared with the temperature sensor's values. The data is resampled in MATLAB and the offset temperature obtained is 12 degree Celsius.

TABLE 1. Response of resistive heater

K_p	$T_R(S)$	$T_P(S)$	PO(%)	$E_{SS}(\%)$
5.5	127	145	5.07%	7.14%
13	140	151	2.44%	7.31%
25	126	145	4.55%	3.80%
40	117	138	5.07%	3.13%

TABLE 2. Response of thermoelectric heater

K_p	$T_R(S)$	$T_P(S)$	PO(%)	$E_{SS}(\%)$
5.5	78	93	6.18%	9.89%
13	58	69	4.23%	1.27%
25	70	87	5.32%	1.11%
40	44	54	4.55%	1.18%

FIGURE 6. Comparison between resistive and thermoelectric heater

FIGURE 7. Temperature offset measurement

FIGURE 8. Ziegler Nichols tuning for 70 degree

FIGURE 9. Ziegler Nichols tuning for 80 degree

Figure 10. Ziegler Nichols tuning for 90 degree

FIGURE 11. Ziegler Nichols tuning for 100 degree

FIGURE 16. Heat and cut splint material

FIGURE 17. Splint material is soften

FIGURE 18. Splint material is cut after softening

Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the PCB design for this paper. Figure 15 shows the controller, cartridge heater, temperature sensor and metal bar are implemented onto a pair of scissors by using 3D printing. The heating bar is placed in front of the scissors so that it can heat up and soft thermoplastics before cutting. The heating bar does not heat the scissors. Therefore, it can protect the scissors from overheating. Figure 16 shows the way to use this prototype. Figure 17 shows the effect of heating from this prototype on a piece of splint material. The targeted area turns into transparent and ready to be cut. Figure 18 shows the outcome after using this prototype.

TABLE 5. Evaluation of this prototype

Thickness(m m)	Temperature(C)	Time(s)
2.4	70	< 10
3.2	90	< 10
4.8	100	< 10

Table 5 is the evaluation for this prototype. The optimum temperature for this prototype to operate is different depends on the thickness of the splint materials. The time required to soften the splint materials is within 10 seconds. The preheat time for the heating element is 3 minutes.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the comparison between Peltier module and cartridge heater is experimented. It is found that the thermoelectric heater has a better performance than the resistive heater. However, the Peltier module required a good cooling system which will increase the overall size of the prototype. Therefore cartridge heater is used throughout this paper. This paper successfully designed a controller which can maintain target temperatures. This prototype has a low steady state error and settling time. The heating tool works well with the scissors. The time to heat and soft the splint materials is within 10 seconds. It is portable and able to soften the splint materials. Therapists can cut splint material without feeling hand pain. The size of the prototype can be improved in the future by using smaller integrated circuit (IC).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work has been supported by research funding from Centre of Research and Instrumentation Management (CRIM), Research University Grant (GUP-2018-048) under Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM).

REFERENCE

- Ahmed, W. A., Aggour, M. & Bennani, F. 2017. Automating a solar water heating system. *Journal of Energy Systems* 1(2): 56–64.
- Álvarez de Miguel, S., Mollocana Lara, J. G., García Cena, C. E., Romero, M., García de María, J. M. & González-Aguilar, J. 2017. Identification model and PI and PID controller design for a novel electric air heater. *Automatika* 58(1): 55–68.
- Fess, E. E. 2002. A History of splinting: To understand the present, view the past. *Journal of Hand Therapy* 15(2): 97–111.
- Harata, I., Takagi, S., Wakabayashi, I., Sakai, M., Tetuka, H. & Toshou, T. 2001. The development of the storage tank water heater by thermoelectric technology. *Seventeenth International Conference on Thermoelectrics. Proceedings ICT98 (Cat. No.98TH8365)*, hlm. 547–550. IEEE.
- Hondianto, T., Susanto, E. & Wibowo, A. S. 2016. Model Driven PID Controller in Water Heater System. *International Journal of*

- Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)* 6(4): 1673–1680.
- Kamus Dewan. 2005. Edisi baru. Kuala Lumpur. Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka.
- Khan, P. F., Sengottuvel, S., Patel, R., Gireesan, K., Baskaran, R. & Mani, A. 2018. Design and Implementation of a Discrete-Time Proportional Integral (PI) Controller for the Temperature Control of a Heating Pad. *SLAS TECHNOLOGY: Translating Life Sciences Innovation* 23(6): 614–623.
- Kumar, S., Gupta, A., Yadav, G. & Singh, H. P. 2015. Peltier module for refrigeration and heating using embedded system. *2015 International Conference on Recent Developments in Control, Automation and Power Engineering (RDCAPE)*, hlm. 314–319. IEEE.
- Li, C., Yu, Y. & Zhang, K. 2011. Superplastic forming of AZ31 magnesium alloy using resistance heating. *Proceedings of 2011 6th International Forum on Strategic Technology*, hlm. 190–193. IEEE.
- Lupi, S., Forzan, M. & Aliferov, A. 2015. Induction and Direct Resistance Heating: Theory and Numerical Modeling, hlm. 2nd Edisi . London: Springer.
- Multicast. 2018. Application Tips for Thermoplastic Splinting. <http://multicast.info/html/orthoticintervention.htm> [26 November 2018].
- Oppelt, T., Schulze, J., Stein, H. & Platzer, B. 2012. *Comparison of methods for mould surface heating-Part 1: Review. International Polymer Science and Technology*, hlm. Vol. 39.
- Shen, Y.-D., Shen, G.-Y., Li, Z.-Z., Ren, M. & Seol, S.-Y. 2010. A Study on Steam Generator for Domestic Steam Cleaner with Cartridge Heater. *2010 Second International Workshop on Education Technology and Computer Science*, hlm. 69–73. IEEE.
- Solutions, P. T. 2015. Make a Resting Splint. <https://www.ptsonline.com/blog/-/blogs/make-a-resting-splint> [26 November 2018].
- Zhang, X. & Zhao, L. D. 2015. Thermoelectric materials: Energy conversion between heat and electricity. *Journal of Materiomics* 1(2): 92–105.